
An Empirical Study on the Changing Status of Women and Social Reforms in Modern India

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ABSTRACT

The position that women are given in a society might be used to gauge its value. The social standing of women has a significant impact on how a community or a nation develops. Women's social standing in a nation reflects the era's social consciousness. Planning regarding women's status is a challenging and complex issue, nevertheless. People's perceptions of women's status have fluctuated throughout history. This paper aims to present the various constraints and social issues associated with the backwardness of women and focuses on the changing role and status of modern Indian women. The research is based entirely on secondary sources. According to paper's needs, the details are obtained from books, magazines, journals, research articles, internet and also from some government documents. An attempt has been made to analyze the evolving position and role of women in contemporary India using these sources. In India, women are now completely involved in a variety of fields, including science, technology, education, sports, politics, media, art, and culture. Thus, women's evolving status and role are crucial to the nation's overall growth.

Introduction

"You can tell the condition of a nation
by looking at the status of its women "

- Jawaharlal Nehru

Male and female, the two basic components of our human society, are interdependent and each of them constitutes almost half of the population. The status of women in society reflects the standard of its civilization. It is evident from our culture that on the one hand women are regarded as symbols of spirituality as Goddesses like Lakshmi, Saraswati, Durga etc., on the other hand all heinous and illegal crimes like rape, social exploitation, kidnapping, female foeticide are being committed against them. In this time, women have made strides because of the proliferation of knowledge and self-awareness. Modern women have power. On top of that, women are making strides and achieving success in every industry.

A. Background of the study

Since freedom, Indian government has decided to grant women and men equal status by development programs. Yet, amid a lot of attempts, women in India are still ill-treated and have a poor ranking relative to males. This research aims to examine the evolving role of modern Indian women and is focused solely on secondary evidence. The study reveals that, while women have made tremendous strides in every field of life in Indian society, they still have to contend against the deep-rooted patriarchal mindset of society. The constitution of India gives women rights to that of men, but has never been successful in bringing about a remarkable shift in the status of modern women. Equalization of men is still a myth for women, since male superiority still prevails in social structure.

There is nothing in men without the contributions of women since they are the cornerstone of civilization. Without women, the creation of a family, which then builds a home, leading to the formation of a community, and ultimately, a nation, would not have been possible. The involvement of women in development activities is, per se, the key to progress in a nation. As Swami Vivekananda very aptly quoted, "The welfare of the world cannot be envisioned unless the condition of women is improved."

In the last few years, the condition of Indian women has improved significantly. Women's position – political, social, economical and general – is far higher today in India than it was in mediaeval and ancient times. While women's position has been taken up in eyes of the law, they are also far from equitable terms with men. In modern Indian culture, women are still abused and embarrassed.

The era after 1750 AD has traditionally been regarded as modern era. The role of women shifts dramatically over this time and can be analysed in two phases.

- Women's status in India under British rule
- Post-independent India women's position.

I. Status of women during British rule in India

The women's status hit the lowest point in society at the advent of the British regime. The role of the wife in the community was in a sad state. The principal reason of this was the existence of male superiority. As a result, the role of women has been weakened. Women's key duties have been committed to the execution of domestic responsibilities and have not been permitted to partake in the implementation of other roles and events, nor have they been allowed to share their thoughts and points of view. In addition, they were overwhelmed by the tradition of polygamy, child marriage, sati and female infanticide. The female literacy was so poor that only one female in hundreds could write or read. Evil civil rituals, dogmatic religious convictions, inhuman belief systems and sinister traditions have caused the highest degree of degradation. Child marriage, compulsory widowhood, devdasi, sati, dowry, purdah, polygamy practice and female infanticide made Indian society stagnant.

However, after years of societal degradation, endless depression, hideous misery and social deterioration in the 19th century, the social reformers were eager to dispel social evil and to awaken people from the oppression imposed on Indian women. IswarChandra, Raja Ram Ray, and numerous other social reformers stressed women's education, the prevention of the child marriage, the abolition of polygamy and the remarriage of widows. Popular sentiment was brought against practice of the 'Sati'.

II. Status of women in post independent India.

Changes have been brought about in women's standing. They are making significant contributions in the areas of religion, politics, culture, economics, and society. A growing number of women are enrolling in schools and going to college. These individuals are earning bachelor's, master's, and doctoral degrees as well as finding work. Reputable corporations, educational institutions, and other fields hire women. These individuals work as physicians, researchers, educators, managers, administrators, directors, politicians, attorneys, engineers, and so on. The most noteworthy aspect of society is thought to be the involvement of women, which is mostly due to shifting values. Women have the ultimate privileges in independent India, but many women are ignorant of their rights. Women who are uneducated are mostly unaware of their rights. A research by Prof. Ram Ahuja reveals that the degree of rights understanding depends on these four factors—

- Women's individual history
- Women's socioeconomic atmosphere
- The economic base of women
- Subjective perception of women

It is also possible to assume that most women are satisfied with their families and leave crucial decisions to their husbands. They are not fully deprived of the conventional practices of culture. Many of them are also exploited, relying solely on their wives. Therefore, increasing laws to ensure equal conditions for women would not help if the Indian culture and the mindset of citizens towards the position of women and women in society would not be significantly altered.

B. Research Problem

Women being the wealth of the Indian culture and have contributed to almost every area and making the nation swell with proud at every chance. They're at the front, leading the nation, creating milestones and a true inspiration for many. India is regarded as having a rich and ancient past, with many female goddesses, saints, and writers adored throughout the world. Even though India is still a powerful nation and is known worldwide as the world's largest democracy, social problems, challenges, and numerous restrictions on women make women's backwardness quite apparent in Indian society. In Indian tradition, it might be argued that

giving birth as a woman is a misfortune. Numerous sociocultural concerns and challenges that Indian women confront have been a major obstacle for them since the beginning of their existence. The role of women in a diverse society like India is not standardised. In comparison, this paper stresses the amount of women in both out-of-workers, tormenting them by men in personal life, in professional life and in the diverse fields in which they are participants. In conclusion, it concludes on the value of women and the role of society in the emancipation of women from patriarchal society and their persecution and concealment.

C. Research Objectives

1. To find out rate of violence against women in India
2. To know the Constitutional and Legislative provisions relating to women in India.
3. To provide some suggestion to overcome of these issues.
4. To provide some suggestion to overcome of these issues.

2. Review of Literature

According to Arpita Banerjee (2013) In India, the role of women during independence was appalling. Women's difficulties in obtaining a comparable degree of ability to associate with schooling, well-being, essential leadership as men owing to the predominance of male-centered society and financial backwardness in India have placed women in the backstage. After autonomy Indian organisers and plan developers viewed the problem and small selection of policies and programmes to grant women the role of men. Northern states like BIMARU also have a long way to go to advance women in India.

As per Dr. Rekha Singh, the status of women in society can be used to gauge the significance of advancement. Women were given a unique place in ancient Indian society, which is one of the few elements that validates its immensity. Women's standing has significantly declined in India as a result of Muslim influence. They were denied the benefits of being treated as citizens. In the direction of this inequality and servitude, Raja Ram Mohan Roy has begun to change. In addition, the way Indian and British cultures interact has changed the role of women. The involvement of women in the Freedom Struggle, which Mahatma Gandhi promoted, was the third factor in reestablishing the role of women. Due to this rise in versatility, Indian women have been segregated as teachers, medical caregivers, airwomen, booking

officers, receptionists, and specialists. They are also involved in government organizations and concerns. In any case, in light of this shift in women's status, the negative aspects of dowries, lack of education, ignorance, and financial slavery must be completely eradicated, with the ultimate goal being to give them their proper place in Indian society.

According to Chandrakala Halli et al. (2016) state that the majority of social reformers have attempted to repair and promote women's brilliance through reading, the press, and the level. Numerous significant reformers played a significant role in this, including Duragabai Deshmukh, Jyotiba Phule, KandukuriVeersalingam, Swami Dayanand, Iswar Chandra Vidyasagar, Raja Ram Mohan Roy, and E. V. Ramaswami. In his capacity as William Bentinck's emissary, Raja Ram Mohan Roy asserted his authority to declare the Sati system unlawful. The Manu rule, which governs the role and behavior of women, has been rigidly upheld for a considerable amount of time in our nation's man-centered family and culture.

3. Research Methodology

The article has a detailed and analytical character. An effort has been made to examine the changing role of women and social changes in modern India. According to the paper's needs, the details used are secondary in nature and are obtained from books, magazines, journals, research articles and also from some government documents.

4. Expected Outcome

India has made impressive strides in empowering women. In fact, the country has the maximum number of highly trained and working women in the world. Women in India are now excellent consultants, specialists, scholars, teachers, and leaders across diverse fields—science, technology, business, politics, and education. This change was brought about through the social reformation efforts of those working for women, so that they could unfold their full potential and challenge generally assigned roles in society. As a result, women enter as well as lead in the hitherto men-dominated fields, greatly contributing to the economic and social development of the country. Progress is, however evident, while challenges such as violence against women and gender discrimination are still there, which requires constant legal reforms and social awareness. The rising number of women leaders is not only a sign that old values

are changing but also the ongoing process of support, education, and empowerment will lead Indian women in making continuous progress.

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